

Principles Of Management of Poisoning in Farm Animals

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Abstract

Plant poisonings in livestock are uncommon, but feed incidents involving some plant components of a diet are more common, and some of these can have serious consequences. It is not uncommon for a wide range of plant by-products to be fed to livestock, the majority of which can be associated with some level of risk. The likelihood of poisoning and subsequent damage in various ruminant species and categories varies according to the animal management system and feeding used. For barn-kept animals, the greatest risk is posed by contaminated or poor-quality feedstuffs (mycotoxins, nitrates, poisonous plants), incorrect doses of substances used as ruminant feed supplements (urea, mineral substances), and incorrect doses of administered drugs. Grazing ruminants, on the other hand, are most vulnerable to poisonous plant ingestion, contaminated water, and zootoxins.

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Introduction

Poisoning is always an emergency and need to be managed immediately with appropriate measures. Intensity of toxicity depends upon the dose and concentration of the poison. Various factors like dose, physio chemical properties, exposure mode, route, age, genetic factors and pathological conditions affect the toxicity.

The 5 basic routes of exposure to poisoning are: ingestion, cutaneous (topical), inhalation, injection (or envenomation) and ocular. Most toxicoses result from the oral ingestion of a toxicant, but some chemicals including many insecticides, phenols and other lipophilic substances may also be efficiently absorbed through intact skin. Abraded skin may absorb some substances that otherwise might not reach toxic concentrations following dermal exposure. Of course, many volatile, aerosolized or even solid particulate agents may be absorbed from the respiratory tract.

Often treatment of a patient must begin before a diagnosis is clearly established. The vast majority of toxic substances do not have specific antidotes and even when an antidote can be used, the

patient will often benefit equally from supportive therapy, which offsets the toxic effects on the animal. In either case logical steps toward preventing further absorption and detoxification of the animal are usually of substantial value.

Basic Principle

“Treat The Patient, Not the Poison”

1) Preventing Continued Absorption/ Decreasing the Exposure

It can be achieved by removal of the poison or source of the poison. In case of the dermal exposure spray must be stopped and skin be thoroughly washed with water. Removal of poison/toxicant from the gut can be achieved by gastric or rumen lavaging / rumenotomy to clear the contents of stomach and washing is preferably done with isotonic normal saline solution or Sodium Bicarbonate solution. However, gastric lavaging should be done with due care and should be avoided in traumatized, anaesthisised or aggressive animals.

- Syrup of ipecac
Dogs: 1 to 2 ml/kg PO
Cats: 3.3 ml/kg PO diluted 50:50 with water
- 3% hydrogen peroxide
1 to 2 ml/kg PO; if no emesis, repeat once
- Apomorphine:
Dogs: 0.03 mg/kg IV or 0.04 mg/kg IM.

If conjunctival route is used, place 1/4 to one 6- mg tablet in the conjunctival sac and dissolve using an ophthalmic irrigating solution. Thoroughly flush any remaining tablet from the sac when emesis begins. Do not use in cats.

- Sodium or magnesium sulfate
Dogs: 5 to 25 g mixed in AC slurry
Cats: 2 to 5 g mixed in AC slurry; give only once
- Saturated solution of sodium chloride
- Xylazine @ 1 mg/Kg B.wt.

2) Removal Of the Toxicant from The Gastrointestinal Tract by Inducing Emesis

Emetics are **never** given to **rodents, rabbits, horses** or **ruminants**. Neither emesis nor gastric lavage are recommended in cases where strong alkali, acid, or other highly corrosive materials have been ingested. Emetics should not be given to animals that are hypoxic, dyspneic, seizing, extremely weak, comatose, lacking normal pharyngeal reflexes, or suffering other marked neurologic impairments that could lead to aspiration pneumonia.

3) Hastening The Passage of The Gut Contents/ Faeces

This should be done in cases where absorption of poison from the lining of the gut is slow. One should be careful while choosing this as it may cause dehydration and several complications which may result into cardiac collapse.

Na₂SO₄ @ 0.5-1 gm/Kg b.wt. PO,

MgSO₄, Paraffin is also used for this purpose in large animals @ 0.5-2 liters

4) Neutralization Of the Poison in The Gut

Neutralisation of poison in gut is achieved by use of chelating agents/adsorbents/neutralizing agents.

A) Chelating agents

- Dimercaprol for Mercury, Arsenic
- Pencillamine: Heavy metal poisoning
- Potassium Permanganate: Used as an oxidizing agent @ 0.5-1 g/Kg as 10-20% solution

B) **Universal antidote:** Activated Charcoal-10 parts, MgO- 5 parts, Kaolin- 5 part

Tannic acid- 5 parts, Water: 200 mL

All animals: 1 to 4 g/kg PO as an aqueous slurry (~1 g per 5 ml water); may be repeated at 4- to 6-hr intervals

5) Enhance The Elimination of The Toxicant from The Body

- **Increase in the rate of glomerular filtration rate** by use of diuretics like furosemide.
- **Reduce the renal tubular reabsorption:** By changing the pH of the medium and ionization of the drug in renal filtrate. In case of weak acid, urinary alkalizers like NH₄Cl (dogs: 100 mg/kg PO bid; Cat: 20 mg/kg PO bid), Ascorbic acid and Na-acid phosphate are used whereas in case of weak alkaline, acidifiers like sodium bicarbonate (1 to 2 m Eq/kg administered every 3 to 4 hr; goal is to achieve urine pH of 7 or greater), Sodium acetate, sodium citrate and Ringer lactate are effective.

Management Goals

Goals for the management of acutely poisoned animals are ordinarily addressed in the following sequence:

- 1.) Stabilize vital signs
- 2.) Clinical evaluation
- 3.) Prevent continued exposure to the toxicant
- 4.) Administer an antidote (if available)
- 5.) Facilitate removal of the absorbed toxicant
- 6.) Supportive therapy and observation.

Stabilizing Vital Signs: The objective is to preserve the life of the animal regardless of the etiology, buying time for detoxification to occur and for specific antidotes to have their pharmacological action.

a) Maintenance of Respiration: It is important to emphasize the needs for:

- 1) A patent airway
- 2) Adequate ventilation and
- 3) Prevention of aspiration of vomitus

b) Maintenance of Cardiovascular Function: Provision of adequate respiratory ventilation, hydration, acid-base, and electrolyte balance are all necessary for normal cardiopulmonary function and oxygen exchange. Certain toxicants cause severe vomiting or diarrhea with resulting electrolyte and fluid imbalances. Ingestion of excessive quantities of drugs, especially diuretics can lead to extreme electrolyte alteration. Furthermore certain toxicants or toxic metabolites, such as oxalic acid may bind calcium sufficiently to result in a hypocalcemic state. Thus, when cardiovascular dysfunction is associated with a toxic insult, correction of imbalances of calcium, sodium, potassium and acid-base status may result in restoration of normal function. Blood samples for electrolyte, blood glucose, and serum chemistry determinations should be collected before initiating fluid therapy. ECGs may be monitored and appropriate measures taken to reestablish homeostasis.

Fluid Therapy

Clinical guides to the assessment of fluid balance include features of serious flow volume overload (e.g., pulmonary edema) and volume contraction (e.g., skin turgor). If shock or hypotension occurs, balanced electrolyte solutions (e.g., lactated Ringer's solution) or normal saline are often indicated.

Specific antidotes

Different antidotes counteract the effect of toxicants in various ways. Many "antidotes" are directed toward achieving stabilization of vital signs, decreasing exposure, or facilitating removal whereas other "antidotes" specifically antagonize the toxicant at a primary or secondary site of action. The excessive reliance on an antidote's action can be dangerous.

Antidotes react with the poison or its receptor or interfere with its metabolic or specific toxic pathway. The use of an antidote does not lessen the importance of thorough detoxification or of supportive therapy.

INDICATIONS	ANTIDOTE	DOSAGE
Acetaminophen	N-Acetylcysteine (NAC)	Loading dose of 140 to 280 mg/kg PO or 140 mg in 5% dextrose/water followed by maintenance dose of 70 mg/kg PO qid for 2 to 3 days.
OP/carbamate insecticides	Atropine sulfate	0.1 to 0.5 mg/kg (given until muscarinic signs controlled), 1/4 initial dose given IV with the remainder given IM or SQ. Administered as needed.
Lead, zinc	CaNa ₂ EDTA	25 mg/kg SC qid as a 1% solution (in 5% dextrose/water) for 5 days. Provide 5- to 7-day rest period between courses of treatment to minimize potential for nephrotoxicity.
Cholecalciferol	Calcitonin	4 to 6 IU SC bid to qid
Ethylene glycol—cat, dog	Ethanol (20%)	Dog: 5.5 ml/kg IV every 4 hr for five treatments then every 6 hr for four treatments. Cat: 5 ml/kg IV qid for five treatments then tid for four treatments. Effective oral dose is estimated to be 2 to 3 ml of 80 proof (40% ethanol) product.
OP insecticides	Pralidoxime chloride(2-PAM)	20 mg/kg IM, SC, or slow IV bid
Lead, arsenic	Succimer	10 mg/kg PO tid for 5 days followed by 10 mg/kg PO bid for 2 wk
Anticoagulant rodenticides	Vitamin K ₁	First generation anticoagulants: 1 mg/kg PO for 4 to 6 days. Second generation anticoagulants: 2.5 to 5 mg/kg PO for 2 to 4 wk
Copper intoxication of sheep	Ammonium tetrathiomolybdate	1.7 to 3.4 mg/day given IV or SC every other day for three treatments.
Arsenic, cyanide	Sodium thiosulfate	30 to 40 mg/kg of a 20% solution IV, may be repeated.
Copper, lead	D-penicillamine	Copper: 10 to 15 mg/kg/day PO (for treatment of chronic copper storedisease in dogs). Lead: 110 mg/kg/day PO for 1 to 2 wk, reevaluate animal 1 wk after initial course, additional treatment may be necessary.
Cyanide	Sodium nitrite	16 mg/kg of a 1% solution IV, given only once.
Iron	Deferoxamine mesylate	Not determined. For humans, suggested dose is 5 g of a 5% solution given orally then 20 mg/kg IM every 4 to 6 hr. If shock is present, dose is 40 mg/kg by IV drip over 4 hr, which is repeated 6 hr later and then 15 mg/kg by IV drip every 8 hr.
Nitrites, chlorates	Methylene blue	Dogs: 8.8 mg/kg of a 1% solution given by slow IV drip. Cats: not recommended Ruminants: 4 to 15 mg/kg IV; may be repeated in 6 to 8 hr.
Arsenic, mercury	Dimercaprol (BAL)	2.5 to 5 mg/kg of a 10% solution in oil IM every 4 hr for 2 days then bid for the next 10 days or until recovery.
Xylazine, amitraz	Yohimbine	Dogs: 0.1 to 0.125 mg/kg IV. Cats: not determined.
Urea	Acetic acid	2% solution (vinegar) orally

References

Gooneratne, S. R., Howell, J. M., & Gawthorne, J. M. (1981). An investigation of the effects of intravenous administration of thiomolybdate on copper metabolism in chronic Cu-poisoned sheep. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 46(3), 469-480.

Humphries, W. R., Morrice, P. C., & Bremner, I. (1988). A convenient method for the treatment of chronic copper poisoning in sheep using subcutaneous ammonium tetrathiomolybdate. *The Veterinary Record*, 123(2), 51-53.